

The Role of Continuing Education in Older Age on Life Satisfaction: The Power of Self-Efficacy

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Abstract

Continuing education may represent an important pathway for maintaining psychological resources and well-being in later life. While prior research has documented positive associations between continuing education in later life and life satisfaction, the underlying psychological mechanisms remain insufficiently understood. This study examines whether self-efficacy mediates the relationship between continuing education and life satisfaction, and whether it is further associated with preventive health behavior. Using cross-sectional data from the German Ageing Survey (DEAS; wave 8, 2022/2023; N = 2,868, 72.1 ± 8.7 years) latent correlations and structural equation modeling were applied. Results show that participation in continuing education is indirectly associated with life satisfaction via self-efficacy. In contrast, self-efficacy did not mediate the relationship between continuing education and preventive health behavior. These findings suggest that continuing education is associated with life satisfaction primarily by strengthening individuals' beliefs in their own competence. At the same time, participation is socially and age-selective, with higher engagement among younger and more resource-rich older adults. Due to the cross-sectional design, causal interpretations remain limited. Overall, the results suggest that continuing education may function as a resource-related context associated with life satisfaction in older age, with self-efficacy representing one potential explanatory pathway.

1. Introduction

Continuing education may represent an important pathway through which individuals maintain psychological resources and well-being in older age. Given the limited resources in the healthcare sector, promoting well-being in older age and thereby enabling older adults to live independently at home for as long as possible has become an important societal goal.

There is growing evidence that continuing education in older age seems to not only expand knowledge and skills, but also supports processes of personal development, as the meaningful shaping of life in older age, and the maintenance and promotion of social participation (Kruse, 2018). Studies examining the benefits of continuing education in later life suggest a positive association between participation and cognitive functioning. For instance, Lenehan et al. (2016) discovered that older adults who participated in educational activities experienced an increase in cognitive reserve compared to a control group over a four-year period. However, these results should be interpreted with caution because baseline differences were not fully accounted for. The study also suggests that cognitively stimulating activities may reduce the risk of mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's-type dementia through neuroplasticity mechanisms. Similarly, Hertzog et al. (2008) conducted a review that highlights the consistent longitudinal effects of cognitively engaging activities on improved cognitive functioning at later measurement points. Beyond cognitive outcomes, continuing education is associated with social integration. The social aspect is a primary motivator for engaging in educational activities (Bjursell, 2019), and participation is linked to reduced loneliness and increased life satisfaction. For example, Shi and Jiang (2024) demonstrate that this relationship is mediated by reduced physical and digital isolation; however, these effects seem to be limited to individuals with lower educational attainment. More broadly, a growing body of literature indicates a positive association between participation in class-based activities among adults aged 60 and over and life satisfaction (e.g., Fang & Sim, 2024). Hoffmann et al. (2020) report a longitudinal relationship between participation in continuing education activities and life satisfaction in the age group 40 to 65 years. Narushima et al. (2013) found that the duration of participation in continuing education was positively associated with well-being among individuals aged 60 and older, with life satisfaction serving as a key indicator. Similarly, Yamashita et al. (2017) found a positive relationship between participation in organized

educational programs and life satisfaction among University of the Third Age participants.

While previous research suggests that participation in continuing education can support cognitive functioning, social engagement, and meaningful aging, less attention has been paid to the psychological mechanisms through which continuing education may influence life satisfaction in later life. In particular, it remains largely unclear whether continuing education contributes to life satisfaction by strengthening individuals' psychological resources. One such resource may be self-efficacy, defined as individuals' beliefs in their ability to successfully manage challenges and achieve desired outcomes (Bandura, 1977; Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 2002). According to Bandura (1977), self-efficacy can emerge from four sources, which can also be observed in learning contexts (Mullen, 2012): 1) performance accomplishments, based on personal mastery experiences, as the most influential source, for example through successfully completing challenging yet manageable tasks; 2) vicarious experience, gained by observing others, particularly those in similar life situations (role models), successfully performing tasks; 3) verbal persuasion, such as encouragement and positive feedback; and 4) emotional arousal, where stress or anxiety (e.g., in testing situations) may undermine self-efficacy. Hammond and Feinstein (2005) demonstrated that participation in educational programs over ten years can increase self-efficacy.

In the geragogical context, self-efficacy has been identified as a motivator for learning that influences performance (Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 2002). However, negative age stereotypes have been shown to diminish self-efficacy in older age, which can reduce motivation to perform (Bubolz-Lutz et al., 2022). Creely and Southcott (2020) demonstrate in their study of a poetry-writing course at a University of the Third Age how different sources of self-efficacy can be activated in learning settings. Participants described how completing challenging tasks under time pressure, such as writing a poem within a limited timeframe, functioned as mastery experiences that increased their confidence in engaging in similar activities in the future. Additionally, observing the achievements of fellow learners and engaging in shared learning processes fostered a sense of capability through vicarious experiences. Verbal persuasion was provided both by the instructor and peers, while the overall positive and supportive learning environment helped transform initial negative emotions into positive feelings and resilience. Jokisch et al. (2022) complement these findings by showing that a

training program aimed at improving digital literacy among older adults enhances general self-efficacy, though it does not increase domain-specific internet self-efficacy.

From a conceptual, health psychology perspective, self-efficacy is closely linked to health behavior, which encompasses "actions taken by individuals that affect health or mortality" (Short & Mollborn, 2015, p. 78). The Health Action Process Approach (HAPA; Schwarzer, 1992) delineates the mechanisms through which alterations in health behavior emerge. The process is comprised of two phases: the motivational phase, in which intentions are formed, and the volitional phase, in which health behaviors are implemented and maintained. Self-efficacy has been identified as a significant predictor in both phases. Grembowski et al. (1993) demonstrated a strong association between self-efficacy and health behavior in older adults in a randomized trial. Similarly, Remm et al. (2023) recently reviewed the existing literature and identified direct and indirect links between self-efficacy and health behavior among older adults.

Self-efficacy can not only lead to changes in health behavior, but can also be an important factor for life satisfaction in older age (Pham & Bhar, 2026). One potential explanation for this pattern is that individuals with higher self-efficacy are more likely to employ adaptive coping strategies. These strategies are designed to proactively modify stressful environmental conditions, thereby converting them into less detrimental circumstances. For instance, this approach can facilitate the management of traumatic experiences (Benight & Bandura, 2004).

In summary, while a substantial body of research highlights the positive effects of continuing education on life satisfaction in later life and the importance of self-efficacy for health-related outcomes, few studies have examined how continuing education and self-efficacy jointly contribute to life satisfaction. This study addresses this gap by examining whether participation in continuing education is associated with higher life satisfaction and whether this relationship operates through increased self-efficacy and, in turn, with preventive health behavior, as shown in Figure 1. By focusing on self-efficacy as a potential explanatory pathway, the study contributes to a better understanding of how educational activities may support psychological well-being in later life. This would thereby characterize continuing education as a preventative and health-promoting strategy for policymakers, local authorities, educational institutions, and social security agencies.

Figure 1

Overview of Associations Examined in our Study

The present study therefore investigates whether participation in continuing education is associated with life satisfaction in later life and whether this association is mediated by self-efficacy. It is hypothesized that increased engagement in continuing education is associated with elevated levels of life satisfaction (H1). We also hypothesize that more frequent participation in continuing education is directly associated with increased self-efficacy and indirectly associated with preventive health behavior, with less smoking and alcohol consumption and more sport and preventive health check-ups as indicators (H2). Third, we expect a positive indirect effect of self-efficacy between continuing education and life satisfaction (H3).

2. Method

2.1 Dataset and Sample

The secondary data analysis was conducted cross-sectionally using wave 8 of the German Ageing Survey (FDZ-DZA, 2025: SUFs DEAS 1996–2023) from the research project 'German Ageing Survey – The Second Half of Life', funded by the Federal Ministry for Family Affairs, Senior Citizens, Women and Youth. Fieldwork took place between December 2022 and June 2023. CAPI and CATI interviews were conducted by the infas Institute for Applied Social Science GmbH on behalf of the German Centre

of Gerontology. Participants received an expense allowance of €15. All participants in the DEAS study provided informed consent prior to the interview. The study complies with the Declaration of Helsinki and its subsequent amendments. Ethical approval was not required, as the study did not meet the criteria for review, for instance, it involved no patient examinations.

For this study, the analysis included all persons aged 60 and over. The resulting sample comprised 2,868 individuals and was weighted according to gender, birth cohort, region and education, in line with the recommendations of the German Centre of Gerontology (Stuth et al., 2025). The sociodemographic characteristics of the participants are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Sample Characteristics (weighted)

Variable	Sample (n = 2.868)
Age in years (M, SD, range)	72.1 ± 8.7; 60–98
Gender	
Female	51.7%
Male	48.3%
Educational Level	
Low	37.3%
Medium	33.2%
High	29.4%
Income in € (M, SD)	3.138,87 ± 2.235,57

2.2 Measures

Life satisfaction was assessed using the Satisfaction With Life Scale (Pavot & Diener, 1993) comprising five items (e.g., 'In most ways, my life is close to my ideal'), scored on a 5-point scale ranging from 'strongly agree' to 'strongly disagree'. A higher value represents greater life satisfaction. *Self-efficacy* was surveyed using the Generalized Self-Efficacy Scale (Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1995) with four items (e.g., 'It is easy for me to stick to my aims and accomplish my goals') on a 4-point scale from 'strongly agree' to 'strongly disagree'. A higher value reflects greater self-efficacy. *Smoking* was measured using the question 'Do you currently smoke – even if it's only occasionally?' with four possible answers ranging from 'I have never smoked' to 'Yes, daily' with a higher value indicating greater cigarette consumption. *Alcohol* consumption was

assessed by asking, 'How often do you have a drink containing alcohol (e.g., beer, wine, sparkling wine, spirits, long drinks)?' and providing six possible answers ranging from 'Never' to 'Daily'. A higher value suggests greater alcohol consumption. *Sport* was surveyed with the question 'How often do you do sports such as hiking, soccer, gymnastics, or swimming?' with six possible answers ranging from 'Never' to 'Daily'. The higher the value, the more frequently sports were practised. *Participation in preventive health check-ups* was measured using three items (e.g., 'In the past years, did you regularly undergo early cancer screening?') from the Federal Health Reporting (2006), each with a dichotomous (yes/no) response. In addition, respondents were asked how often they attend courses or lectures for *continuing education*, with six possible answers ranging from 'Never' to 'Daily', where a higher value reflects more frequent participation. Age, education, gender, and income were included as sociodemographic variables.

2.3 Statistical Analyses

Latent correlations were performed to examine the association between individual study variables, with effect size criteria interpreted according to Cohen (1988; 0.1 = small, 0.3 = medium, 0.5 = large).

The simultaneous association in the overall model was tested using a structural equation model (SEM). Continuing education, smoking, alcohol consumption, sports, and preventive health check-ups (mean score) entered the model as manifest variables, whereas self-efficacy and life satisfaction, were modeled as latent constructs. Prior to the structural analysis, construct reliability and validity were evaluated using a measurement model based on confirmatory factor analysis. The comparative fit index (CFI > .95: good), root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA < .80: acceptable), and standardized root mean square residual (SRMR < .80: acceptable) were used as indicators of goodness of fit according to the thresholds of Hu & Bentler (1999). Composite reliability (> .70: acceptable; Hair, 2023) was used for reliability, average variance extracted (> .50: acceptable; Hair, 2023) for convergent validity. Given the presence of ordinal indicators, estimation relied on the weighted least squares mean and variance adjusted (WLSMV) estimator, which provides robust parameter estimates under non-normality. In the estimation process of the SEM, age, education, gender, and income were integrated as manifest control variables; the use of auxiliary variables was eschewed. Indirect effects were estimated using the delta

method with robust (mean- and variance-adjusted) standard errors as implemented in the WLSMV estimator. Missing data were handled using listwise deletion, which is the default approach for models estimated with the WLSMV estimator and categorical indicators. No post hoc model modifications were performed. The analysis was conducted with the R 4.5.2 software and the 'lavaan' package (Rosseel, 2012).

3. Results

3.1 Sociodemographic Differences in Participation in Continuing Education

As shown in Table 1, there were significant differences in average age ($t(1958) = 8.27$, $p < .001$, $d = .32$) between participants and non-participants in continuing education, with a medium effect size. Participants were on average 71.0 ± 8.0 years old, while non-participants were on average 73.6 ± 8.0 years old. Regarding gender, no significant difference was observed ($\chi^2(1) = 0.01$, $p = .738$, $\phi = .01$). Higher levels of education ($\chi^2(2) = 197.07$, $p < .001$, $\phi = .26$) and income ($\chi^2(3) = 88.75$, $p < .001$, $\phi = .18$) were significantly associated with higher participation in continuing education, with a small effect sizes. While only 12.86% of respondents with a monthly net household income below €2,000 participated in continuing education, more than half (63.77%) of those with €3,000 or more did so.

Table 1

Results of χ^2 -/t-Test (Age, Gender, Education, Income) for Participation in Continuing Education within Sociodemographic Groups

Variable	Participants	χ^2 -/t-test	p-value	Effect Size ^b
Age (mean, SD)	71.0 ± 8.0	$t(1958) = 8.27$	< .001	$d = .32$
Gender ^a		$\chi^2(1) = 0.01$.738	$\phi = .01$
Female	32.86%			
Male	32.21%			
Level of Education		$\chi^2(2) = 197.07$	< .001	$\phi = .26$
Lower Secondary Education	18.24%			
Secondary School Diploma				
University Entrance Qualification and Higher	28.14% 47.86%			
Net Household Income		$\chi^2(3) = 88.75$	< .001	$\phi = .18$
€0 to under €1,000	0.86%			
€1,000 to under €2,000	12.00%			
€2,000 to under €3,000	23.37%			

€3,000 and more

63.77%

Note. Participation in continuing education no = 0, yes = 1.

^a m = 1, f = 2.

^b Interpretation according to Cohen (1988): $d > .20$ = small, $> .50$ = medium, $> .80$ = large; Φ : $> .1$ = small, $> .3$ = medium, $> .5$ = large.

3.2 Latent Correlations and Structural Equation Model for the Relationships between the Study Variables

With regard to latent correlations (see Table 2), self-efficacy was strongly ($r = .69$) positively correlated with life satisfaction. Relevant to our study, participation in continuing education was weakly positively correlated with both self-efficacy ($r = .16$) and life satisfaction ($r = .17$). Furthermore, an association was observed between participation in continuing education and preventive health behaviors, specifically a small positive effect on sport ($r = .24$), alcohol consumption ($r = .11$), and smoking ($-.03$). Additionally, sport ($r = .21$), alcohol consumption ($r = .16$), and smoking ($r = -.04$) were positively correlated with life satisfaction, albeit with small effects.

Table 2

Latent Correlations of the Study Variables

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Self-Efficacy	—							
2. Life Satisfaction	.69***	—						
3. Continuing Education	.16***	.17***	—					
4. Educational Level	.16***	.13***	.28***	—				
5. Sport	.18***	.21***	.24***	.23***	—			
6. Health Screen	-.01	.06**	.04*	.01	.11***	—		
7. Alcohol	.10***	.16***	.11***	.21***	.17***	.04*	—	
8. Smoking	.06**	-.04*	-.03*	.02	-.09***	-.08***	.05**	—

Note. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Effect size classes: $r > .10$: small, $r > .30$: moderate, $r > .50$: large

VIF values ranged from 1.04 to 1.16, and tolerance ranged from 0.86 to 0.96, indicating no multicollinearity. Confirmatory factor analysis yielded an acceptable to good model fit (CFI = .981, RMSEA = .054, SRMR = .048). The standardized factor loadings ranged from .51 to .82. The average variance extracted (AVE) for life satisfaction reached an acceptable level (.51). The limited convergent validity of the self-efficacy construct (AVE = .33) and its borderline reliability (CR = .67) are likely related to the use of a

short scale. While short instruments reduce respondent burden, they typically capture less variance of the underlying construct, which may compromise measurement precision. However, composite reliability for life satisfaction (.83) indicated an overall satisfactory level of internal consistency. In addition, the HTMT ratio (.661) provided support for discriminant validity between the constructs. The structural equation model demonstrated an acceptable overall fit to the data (CFI = .937, RMSEA = .057, SRMR = .046). The model explained a substantial proportion of variance in life satisfaction (55.6%). This comparatively high level of explained variance may be attributable to the strong association with self-efficacy, which was already evident in the latent correlations. The explained variance in self-efficacy was modest ($R^2 = .09$). For the health behavior outcomes, the proportion of explained variance was generally low, with 15% for sport, 10% for smoking, 13% for alcohol consumption, and 2% for preventive health check-ups. The results of the SEM showed a positively significant relationship between participation in continuing education and self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.095, p < .001$), but no significant relationship between educational status and self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.043, p = .079$). As already apparent at the correlational level, there was a strong positive association between self-efficacy and life satisfaction ($\beta = 0.699, p < .001$). With regard to preventive health behaviors, self-efficacy was significantly associated with more frequent sport ($\beta = 0.138, p < .001$), while no associations were observed between self-efficacy and smoking ($\beta = 0.000, p = .991$), alcohol consumption ($\beta = 0.041, p = .068$), or preventive health check-ups ($\beta = -.0021, p = .369$). Higher life satisfaction was associated with alcohol consumption ($\beta = 0.059, p = .001$) and participation in preventive health check-ups ($\beta = 0.035, p = .045$), while no connection to smoking ($\beta = -0.003, p = .868$) and more frequent sport ($\beta = 0.012, p = .569$) was observed. There was an indirect effect of self-efficacy between participation in continuing education and life satisfaction ($\beta = 0.096, p = .007$). There was no indirect effect of self-efficacy between participation in continuing education and the four areas of preventive health behavior.

The examination of the moderator variables reveals a positive association between age and life satisfaction ($\beta = 0.196, p < .001$), as well as a negative association between age and self-efficacy ($\beta = -0.207, p < .001$). Furthermore, older age is negatively associated with sport ($\beta = -0.061, p = 0.002$) and smoking ($\beta = -0.295, p < .001$). Women reported higher life satisfaction ($\beta = 0.146, p < .001$) than men. Women also engage in sports more frequently ($\beta = 0.174, p < .001$) and smoke ($\beta = -0.116, p$

< .001) and drink ($\beta = -0.150, p < .001$) less often. Furthermore, they undergo more preventive health check-ups ($\beta = 0.041, p = .037$). Individuals with higher incomes reported significantly higher life satisfaction ($\beta = 0.204, p < .001$) and self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.109, p < .001$). They also report engaging in more sport ($\beta = 0.305, p < .001$), smoking less frequently ($\beta = -0.146, p < .001$), drinking more alcohol ($\beta = 0.272, p < .001$) and attending more preventive health check-ups ($\beta = 0.157, p < .001$). A higher level of education is associated with younger age ($\beta = -0.165, p < .001$), female gender ($\beta = 0.040, p = .039$), and higher income ($\beta = 0.360, p < .001$). Similarly, participation in continuing education is associated with younger age ($\beta = -0.092, p < .001$), female gender ($\beta = 0.111, p < .001$), and higher income ($\beta = 0.270, p < .001$).

Table 3: Direct and Indirect Results of the SEM

Path	<i>b</i>	SE	<i>p</i>	95% CI	β
Life Satisfaction ← Smoking	-0.00	.01	.868	[-0.025, 0.022]	-.00
Life Satisfaction ← Alcohol	0.03	.01	.001	[0.010, 0.040]	.59
Life Satisfaction ← Sport	0.00	.01	.569	[-0.011, 0.019]	.01
Life Satisfaction ← Preventive Health Check-Ups	0.07	.04	.045	[0.001, 0.140]	.04
Life Satisfaction ← Self-Efficacy	1.05	.05	< .001	[0.947, 1.148]	.70
Life Satisfaction ← Age	0.02	.00	< .001	[0.013, 0.019]	.20
Life Satisfaction ← Gender	0.21	.03	< .001	[0.152, 0.258]	.15
Life Satisfaction ← Income	0.17	.02	< .001	[0.133, 0.210]	.20
Life Satisfaction ← Continuing Education	0.11	.04	.007	[0.032, 0.196]	.10
Smoking ← Self-Efficacy	0.00	.05	.991	[-0.088, 0.089]	.00
Smoking ← Continuing Education	-0.00	.01	.619	[-0.019, 0.011]	-.00
Alcohol ← Self-Efficacy	0.15	.08	.068	[-0.011, 0.304]	.04

Alcohol	←	Continuing Education	0.02	.01	.263	[-0.012, .01043]
Sport	←	Self-Efficacy	0.55	.10	< .001	[0.358, .740]
Sport	←	Continuing Education	0.05	.03	.058	[-0.002, .020110]
Preventive Health Check-Up	←	Self-Efficacy	-0.02	.02	.369	[-0.049, -.020018]
Preventive Health Check-Up	←	Continuing Education	-0.00	.00	.845	[-0.006, -.000005]
Self-Efficacy	←	Educational Level	0.03	.01	.079	[-0.003, .040053]
Self-Efficacy	←	Continuing Education	0.06	.01	< .001	[0.031, .100086]

CFI = .937, RMSEA = .057, SRMR = .046. Gender: 1 = male, 2 = female.

Graphic 1: Results of the SEM

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$ ***, $p < .001$. CFI = .937, RMSEA = .057, SRMR = .046.

4. Discussion

The present study sought to examine the association between participation in continuing education among older adults and life satisfaction, and to determine the role of self-efficacy and preventive health behaviors in this context.

4.1 Associations between Education, Self-Efficacy, Preventive Health Behavior and Life Satisfaction

The findings of the latent correlations indicate that participation in continuing education is positively associated with higher life satisfaction, thereby supporting *H1* and underscoring the non-monetary value of continuing education in later life. Our findings further corroborate existing literature indicating that life satisfaction tends to increase with age, a widely observed phenomenon often referred to as the “paradox of well-being” (Hansen & Blekesaune, 2022). At the same time, participation in continuing education is negatively associated with age, indicating that relatively younger individuals within the older population are more likely to engage in such activities. The observed association between continuing education and life satisfaction is likely driven primarily by a subgroup of comparatively younger and more resource-rich older adults who remain active in educational contexts. This interpretation is consistent with research suggesting that well-being may plateau or decline in more advanced stages of old age (Hansen & Blekesaune, 2022). Accordingly, the findings point to the heterogeneity of ageing: opportunities for participation in continuing education and their associated well-being benefits are not evenly distributed but are concentrated among those with more favorable resource profiles (e.g., health, cognitive capacity, motivation). This pattern is also reflected in the distribution of financial resources within our sample, where individuals with higher incomes tend to be more likely to participate in continuing education. Lower participation in continuing education among older individuals may be interpreted in light of socioemotional selectivity theory (Carstensen, 1993), which posits a shift in goal orientation from knowledge-related to emotionally meaningful goals with increasing age. However, age differences in participation may not solely reflect motivational factors but may also be associated with physical limitations, such as reduced mobility and sensory impairments, that can constrain participation.

Participation in continuing education was positively associated with self-efficacy, consistent with prior research suggesting that learning activities can foster psychosocial resources in later life. However, self-efficacy did not mediate the relationship between continuing education and preventive health behaviors. Thus, *H2* was only partially supported. While theoretical frameworks such as the Health Action Process Approach (HAPA) emphasize a positive association between self-efficacy and health behavior, the focused general self-efficacy strengthened through educational participation may not be sufficiently domain-specific to translate into specific health-related action. Furthermore, our results show that women exhibit more favorable

preventive health behaviors across all domains assessed. This aligns with prior research. For instance, Crimmins et al. (2010) examined gender differences in health behaviors among individuals aged 50 and older across 12 countries and found that men in Germany, as well as in most other countries, were more likely to smoke. Similarly, the review by Hiller et al. (2017) concluded that, in the majority of studies, women tend to be more health-conscious and more engaged in preventive health practices. However, in contrast to our findings, some studies report that men are more physically active in terms of sports participation. In light of the increasingly important role of digitalization, previous research indicates that being female is associated with higher use of health-related mobile applications (Escoffery, 2018). Furthermore, individuals with higher income levels in our study generally exhibit more favorable preventive health behaviors. Pampel et al. (2010) showed that individuals with lower income have higher odds of smoking and physical inactivity, even after controlling for other socioeconomic status indicators (education, occupation, employment, wealth). One possible explanation of the authors relates to higher opportunity costs of time, as time may carry greater economic value in occupational contexts. The only exception in our results is the consumption of alcohol, where a negative association with income was observed; this finding is consistent with the systematic review by Khamis et al. (2022).

The most salient contribution of the present study is the identification of self-efficacy as a central mediating factor between continuing education and life satisfaction, thereby confirming *H3*. The results underscore that continuing educational appears to enhance well-being primarily insofar as it is associated with individuals' beliefs in their own competence. Especially against the backdrop of age-related changes, continuing education can thus be understood as a resource-oriented intervention that contributes to stabilizing or increasing life satisfaction by strengthening self-efficacy (Kruse, 2018). This finding is consistent with Bandura's social cognitive theory (1977), particularly the notion that mastery experiences constitute the most powerful source of self-efficacy. Continuing education can be conceptualized as an enabling structure that provides older adults with opportunities to engage in cognitively and socially meaningful activities. These experiences may reinforce perceived competence and control, which in turn facilitate adaptive coping, sustained goal engagement, and more positive self-appraisals of aging (Bandura, 1977). In this sense, self-efficacy functions as a key

psychological resource that translates learning experiences into broader gains in life satisfaction as one indicator for well-being.

These results resonate with lifespan developmental frameworks such as Selection, Optimization, and Compensation and theories of control beliefs in aging. Rather than assuming a uniform decline, ageing is characterized by domain-specific changes in resources, which may increase the relevance of subjective resources such as self-efficacy for maintaining life satisfaction in some contexts. In this sense, continuing education may function as an optimization strategy by supporting individuals in maintaining engagement despite age-related changes. Self-efficacy, in turn, can be understood as an important psychological resource that may facilitate the effective use of such strategies. This interpretation highlights its role as a potential resource that supports adaptive functioning in later life.

At the same time, the cross-sectional design precludes causal inference, and the observed associations should be interpreted with caution. In particular, participation in continuing education is likely to be positively selective. As mentioned before, individuals who engage in such activities tend to differ systematically from non-participants in terms of health, motivation, cognitive resources, and prior educational experiences. Moreover, reverse and reciprocal relationships are plausible: individuals with higher self-efficacy may be more likely to engage in continuing education in the first place, and continued participation may further reinforce these beliefs over time. The present findings may therefore reflect, at least in part, underlying selection processes rather than causal effects. Future longitudinal and experimental studies are needed to disentangle these dynamics and to test whether changes in self-efficacy indeed mediate the effects of continuing education among older adults on life satisfaction over time.

The findings carry practical implications. If self-efficacy constitutes one pathway linking continuing education to life satisfaction, educational programs should be designed not only to transmit knowledge but to systematically foster mastery experiences. Structuring learning environments to enable incremental success, providing competence-reinforcing feedback, and facilitating constructive social comparison may be particularly effective in strengthening self-efficacy and, consequently, enhancing the psychological benefits of lifewide learning.

4.2 Limitations and Future Studies

These findings should be interpreted in light of several limitations. First, continuing education was measured in relatively broad terms. The assessment was based on a single item and did not include detailed information on the content, quality, duration, or intensity of continuing education activities. Consequently, it remains unclear which specific forms of continuing education (e.g., formal vs. non-formal, health-related vs. general education) are decisive for the observed associations. Future studies should therefore measure continuing education in a multidimensional manner and evaluate it in a more differentiated way in order to make more precise statements about the role of continuing education on life satisfaction.

Second, the sample includes individuals aged 60 and older, including participants who are still employed. Although the item on continuing education explicitly targeted activities outside the work context, it cannot be ruled out that respondents also included professionally motivated continuing education measures. In this case, different reasons for participation (e.g., labor market-related vs. intrinsic motivation) could be associated with different mechanisms of action and effects on self-efficacy and life satisfaction. Future research should therefore differentiate more clearly between employed and non-employed (or no longer employed) individuals and systematically assess the motivations for continuing education.

Third, the study is based on a cross-sectional design, meaning that no causal conclusions can be drawn. The reported findings indicate associations between continuing education, self-efficacy, and life satisfaction; however, they do not permit conclusions regarding the temporal ordering or causal direction of these relationships. For example, it is equally conceivable that individuals with higher self-efficacy or life satisfaction are more likely to participate in continuing education programs. Longitudinal studies are necessary to empirically test the hypothesized pathways and confirm causal relationships.

Fourth, the present study focuses on self-efficacy and preventive health behaviors as potential explanatory pathways between continuing education and life satisfaction. As a result, potentially relevant alternative explanatory approaches are not considered, such as social integration, cognitive stimulation, experiences of meaning and purpose, or perceived autonomy. Future studies should include a broader spectrum of potential

mediators to provide a more comprehensive picture of the underlying mechanisms of action. At the same time, this focus is a strength of the study, as it provides evidence-based insights into the previously understudied role of self-efficacy and preventive health behaviors in the association.

4.3 Conclusion

This study suggests that participation in continuing education in later life is associated with outcomes that extend beyond mere knowledge acquisition. Specifically, it is linked to higher levels of life satisfaction, with self-efficacy emerging as a key explanatory mechanism underlying this relationship. These findings highlight the importance of considering educational engagement as a resource for strengthening psychological capacities among older adults. From a broader perspective, continuing education may thus represent a relevant avenue for promoting well-being in ageing populations, particularly when it fosters individuals' sense of competence and agency.

Declarations

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